

Local extrema of apparent brightness from other planet's position in solar system in the year 2015 and further extrema

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2015

An observer stays in a space ship that circles round a planet.

Explanations:

mag= stellar magnitude,

°=deg,

'=angular minute,

"=angular second,

AE = astronomical unit = 149598500 km

Venus seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
28.2.-5.3. 2015	-4.90	4.76-8.43 increasing	99-100 decreasing	1.18	14.2	0.72
5.5.-6.5. 2015	-7.51	159.78 - 168.53 decreasing	99-100 decreasing	0.36	46.4	0.72

Earth seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
31.1.-1.2. 2015	-4.52	163.15 - 168.36 decreasing	99-100 decreasing	0.66	26.6	0.99
3.4.-6.4. 2015	-2.92	11.07-19.63 decreasing	99-100 increasing	1.34	13.1	1.00

Mars seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mars to Sun [AE]
2.1.-5.1. 2015	-0.49	158.31-171.85	99-100 increasing	1.02	9.1	1.38-1.39 increasing

		increasing				
19.2.-28.2. 2015	+0.85	10.32-26.63 increasing	99-100 decreasing	1.81-1.84 decreasing	5.1-5.2 increasing	1.41-1.43 increasing

Jupiter seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Jupiter to Sun [AE]
30.1.-5.2. 2015	-2.30	155.62 - 170.62 decreasing	100	5.00	39.5	5.33
21.3-27.3. 2015	-1.98	5.75-19.34 decreasing	100	5.75-5.76 decreasing	34.3-34.4 increasing	5.35

Saturn seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Saturn to Sun [AE]
17.1-18.1. 2015	+1.14	3.39-8.83 decreasing	100	10.27	16.2 R=37.7	9.96
23.2-7.3. 2015	+0.97	158.75 - 164.54 decreasing	100	9.53	17.5 R=40.6	9.96-9.97 increasing

Uranus seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Uranus to Sun [AE]
4.1.-13.1. 2015	+5.62	148.30 - 166.62 increasing	100	19.69	3.3 R=13.7	20.01
7.2.-28.2. 2015	+5.70	27.00 - 43.28 increasing	100	20.33-20.34 increasing	3.2 R=13.3	20.00

Neptune seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Neptune to Sun [AE]
1.2.-13.2. 2015	+7.77	15.63-35.97 increasing	100	30.30	2.2 R=5.7	29.97
23.3.-4.4. 2015	+7.71	146.18 - 166.53 increasing	100	29.61	2.3 R=5.9	29.97

Pluto seen from Mercury:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mercury [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Pluto to Sun [AE]
22.1.-1.2. 2015	+15.03	22.05-35.60 increasing	100	33.08-33.09 decreasing	0.096	32.80-32.81 increasing
2.3.-23.3. 2015	+14.98	141.94 - 155.65 increasing	100	32.44-32.46 decreasing	0.098	32.82-32.84 increasing
19.1.-29.1. 2113	+16.76	141.19 - 151.56 increasing	100	49.04	0.065	49.32
28.2.-12.3. 2113	+16.80	18.35-28.91 increasing	100	49.73	0.064	49.32

Mercury seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mercury to Sun [AE]
23.1.-25.1. 2015	-2.07	21.33-22.23 decreasing	72-77 increasing	0.81-0.84 increasing	8.0-8.3 decreasing	0.31
4.3.-8.3. 2015	-0.94	5.00-6.63 increasing	99-100 decreasing	1.18	5.7	0.47
13.4.-15.4. 2015	-1.99	24.66-25.29 increasing	60-68 decreasing	0.71-0.77 decreasing	8.7-9.4 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
3.5. 2015	weaker than +4.00	3.26-3.28 increasing	<1	0.36	18.6	0.36

Earth seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
13.8.-18.8. 2015	-6.23	167.37 - 168.38 decreasing	99-100 decreasing	0.29	60.6	1.01
31.5.-22.6. 2016	-2.34	2.31-6.19 increasing	99-100 decreasing	1.73	10.1	1.01-1.02 increasing

Mars seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in Per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mars to Sun [AE]
26.1.-1.2. 2015	-1.36	169.60 - 175.73 increasing	99-100 increasing	0.68	13.7	1.40
26.7.-14.8. 2015	+1.63	4.92-19.69 increasing	99-100 decreasing	2.28-2.33 decreasing	4.0-4.1 increasing	1.60-1.62 increasing

Jupiter seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Jupiter to Sun [AE]
19.4.-30.4. 2015	-2.45	168.02 - 170.78 increasing	100	4.65	42.5	5.35-5.36 increasing
12.8.-3.9. 2015	-1.84	12.65-15.69 increasing	100	6.09	32.5	5.38-5.39 increasing

Saturn seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Saturn to Sun [AE]
19.2.-18.3. 2015	+1.22	18.84-20.27 increasing	100	10.64-10.65 decreasing	15.6 R=36.4	9.96-9.97 increasing
14.6.-7.7. 2015	+0.92	160.64 - 161.68 increasing	100	9.29-9.30 decreasing	17.9 R=41.7	9.98-9.99 increasing

Uranus seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Uranus to Sun [AE]
23.1.-19.2. 2015	+5.58	157.90 - 158.20 decreasing	100	19.33	3.4 R=13.9	20.00
10.5.-16.6. 2015	+5.73	28.28-28.71 decreasing	100	20.62-20.63 increasing	3.2 R=13.1	19.99-20.00 decreasing

Neptune seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Neptune to Sun [AE]
14.4.-24.5. 2015	+7.79	31.33-31.36 decreasing	100	30.58	2.2 R=5.7	29.97
6.8.-14.9. 2015	+7.69	148.69 - 148.70 decreasing	100	29.34	2.3 R=5.9	29.96

Pluto seen from Venus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Venus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Pluto to Sun [AE]
19.3.-18.4. 2015	+15.06	19.96-26.83 increasing	100	33.49-33.51 decreasing	0.095	32.83-32.86 increasing
8.7.-1.8. 2015	+14.97	157.12 - 163.66 increasing	100	32.22-32.24 decreasing	0.098-0.099 increasing	32.90-32.92 increasing
24.3.-24.4. 2113	+16.81	27.47-28.16 increasing	100	49.96	0.064	49.32
3.7.-27.8. 2113	+16.75	133.20 - 133.78 increasing	100	48.82	0.065	49.32

Mercury seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent Brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°}	Phase in per cent	Distance to Mars [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mercury to Sun [AE]
6.1.2015	weaker than +7.00	1.51-1.53 decreasing	<1	1.02	6.6	0.36-0.37 decreasing

28.1.-31.1.2015	-0.71	9.43-10.82 decreasing	79-87 increasing	1.56-1.63 increasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.32-0.34 increasing
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Venus seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Mars [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
31.1.2015	weaker than +4.00	2.09	<1	0.68	24.6	0.73
15.4.-27.4.2015	-3.57	26.12-28.22 decreasing	61-71 increasing	1.47-1.64 increasing	10.2-11.4 decreasing	0.71-0.72 increasing

Earth seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Mars [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
7.7.-28.8.2015	-1.46	4.19-13.63 increasing	99-100 decreasing	2.52-2.59 decreasing	6.8-7.0 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
2.2.-24.2.2016	-1.78	36.90-36.99 increasing	41-53 decreasing	1.13-1.35 decreasing	13.0-15.6 increasing	0.98-0.99 increasing

Jupiter seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Mars [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Jupiter to Sun [AE]
11.11-12.12.2015	-2.89	170.00 - 173.92 increasing	99-100 increasing	3.75-3.76 decreasing	52.5-52.7 increasing	5.40-5.41 increasing
10.12.2016-24.1.2017	-1.56	5.11-13.88 increasing	99-100 decreasing	6.83-6.85 decreasing	28.8-28.9 increasing	5.45-5.46 increasing

Saturn seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Mars [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Saturn to Sun [AE]
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21.4.-19.6. 2015	+1.38	5.45-20.35 increasing	99-100 decreasing	11.43-11.45 decreasing	14.5-14.6 increasing R=33.8- 33.9	9.97-9.99 increasing
14.5.-21.6. 2016	+0.75	162.58 - 174.06 increasing	99-100 increasing	8.53-8.56 decreasing	19.4-19.5 increasing R=45.2- 45.3	10.02-10.04 increasing

Uranus seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Mars [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Uranus to Sun [AE]
28.1.-14.3. 2015	+5.50	161.67 - 169.47 decreasing	100	18.62-18.64 increasing	3.5 R=14.5	20.00-20.01 decreasing
7.1.-24.3. 2016	+5.82	11.33-20.46 decreasing	100	21.51-21.53 increasing	3.0 R=12.5	19.96-19.98 decreasing

Neptune seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Mars [AE]	Apparent Diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Neptune to Sun [AE]
27.10.- 24.12. 2015	+7.86	11.35-12.26 decreasing	100	31.58-31.59 increasing	2.1 R=5.5	29.96
30.9.-13.12. 2016	+7.64	155.12 - 156.23 decreasing	100	28.68	2.4 R=6.1	29.95

Pluto seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Mars [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Pluto to Sun [AE]
2.8.-4.9. 2015	+15.13	4.05-17.25 increasing	100	34.50-34.53 decreasing	0.092	32.92-32.95 increasing
12.6.-6.9. 2016	+14.96	145.14 - 162.62 increasing	100	31.82-31.88 decreasing	0.10	33.11-33.17 increasing
29.11.2113- 27.3.2114	+16.84	27.52-35.23 decreasing	100	50.64-50.65 increasing	0.059	49.32
2.12.2114-	+16.71	158.09 -	100	47.93	0.062	49.32

8.1.2115		163.26 increasing				
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Mercury seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter [']	Distance from Mercury to Sun [AE]
4.1.-7.1. 2015	+2.09	1.91-2.50 increasing	88-94 decreasing	5.59-5.65 decreasing	1.2	0.35-0.38 decreasing
31.1.2015	weaker than +10.00	0.41-0.42 increasing	<1	5.00	1.3	0.34

Venus seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter [']	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
26.4.2015	weaker than +9.00	0.35	<1	4.64	3.6	0.72
18.8.-26.8. 2015	-1.32	0.70-0.79 increasing	99-100 decreasing	6.11	2.7	0.73

Earth seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter [']	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
6.2.2015	weaker than +14.00	0.18	<1	4.35	4.0	0.99
22.8.-9.9. 2015	+0.48	0.64-1.90 increasing	99-100 decreasing	6.38-6.40 decreasing	2.7-2.8 increasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing

Mars seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter [']	Distance from Mars to Sun [AE]
1.12.2015	weaker than +18.00	0.26	<1	3.74	2.5	1.67
22.11.-28.11. 2016	+3.66	2.58-3.25 decreasing	98-100 increasing	6.79-6.82 increasing	1.4	1.38-1.39 increasing

Saturn seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Saturn to Sun [AE]
31.8.-13.12.2020	-0.47	172.87 - 175.34 increasing	99-100 increasing	4.88-4.90 increasing	33.9-34.0 R=79.1-79.2 decreasing	9.98-10.01 decreasing
12.7.2028-2.1.2030	+1.70	6.70-20.28 decreasing	98-100 increasing	14.16-14.49 increasing	11.5-11.8 R=26.7-27.3 decreasing	9.12-9.25 decreasing

Uranus seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Uranus to Sun [AE]
1.2.-25.8.2017	+6.17	2.34-8.20 decreasing	100	25.35-25.93 decreasing	2.5-2.6 increasing R=4.8	19.91-19.94 decreasing
13.2.-26.6.2024	+4.93	168.98 - 176.71 decreasing	99-100 decreasing	14.61-14.63 increasing	4.4-4.5 decreasing R=18.4	19.58-19.61 decreasing

Neptune seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Neptune to Sun [AE]
19.6.2015-11.5.2016	+8.10	8.42-11.24 increasing	100	35.26-35.28 increasing	1.9 R=4.9	29.91-29.92 decreasing
25.2.-1.9.2022	+7.34	169.76 - 171.09 increasing	100	25.00-25.01 increasing	2.7 R=6.9	29.91-29.92 decreasing

Pluto seen from Jupiter:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Jupiter [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Pluto to Sun [AE]
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13.12.2019-4.7.2020	+14.81	158.62 - 177.33 increasing	99-100 increasing	28.91-29.01 decreasing	0.11	33.93-34.08 increasing
22.11.2026-15.6.2027	+15.67	9.90-22.83 increasing	99-100 decreasing	40.68-40.88 decreasing	0.078	35.64-35.79 increasing
26.9.2118-20.6.2119	+16.55	158.32 - 161.24 decreasing	100	44.54-44.56 increasing	0.071	49.26-49.28 decreasing
12.1.-21.5.2125	+16.98	11.92-14.62 decreasing	100	54.28-54.31 increasing	0.058	49.04-49.06 decreasing

Mercury seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mercury to Sun [AE]
18.1.-20.1.2015	+2.86	0.09-0.38 increasing	98-100 decreasing	10.26-10.27 decreasing	0.66	0.30-0.31 decreasing
28.2.2015	weaker than +14.00	0.15-0.16 increasing	<1	9.51	0.71	0.46

Venus seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
27.2.-11.3.2015	-0.12	0.53-0.67 increasing	99-100 decreasing	10.67-10.68 decreasing	1.6	0.72-0.73 decreasing
10.2.2016	weaker than +12.00	0.10	<1	9.29	1.8	0.73

Earth seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
23.5.2015	weaker than +13.00	0.22	<1	8.97	2.0	1.01

29.11.-4.12. 2015	+1.60	0.18-0.41 increasing	99-100 decreasing	10.99	1.6	0.99
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Mars seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mars to Sun [AE]
7.3.-7.4. 2015	+4.90	1.70-3.72 decreasing	94-99 increasing	11.22-11.40 increasing	0.8	1.42-1.47 increasing
12.6-13.6 2016	weaker than +5.00	0.41-0.42 decreasing	<1	8.54	1.1	1.49

Jupiter seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Jupiter to Sun [AE]
2.11.2020	weaker than +17.00	0.13	<1	4.88	40.5	5.12
12.6.2024	-0.15	29.70-29.71 decreasing	65	9.89	20.0	5.02

Uranus seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Uranus to Sun [AE]
22.7.-26.11. 2032	+4.05	173.42 - 177.58 decreasing	99-100 decreasing	10.03-10.04 increasing	6.5 R=26.9	19.02-19.05 decreasing
15.4.-30.8. 2056	+6.19	1.58-3.21 decreasing	100	27.74-27.76 decreasing	2.3 R=9.7	18.35-18.37 increasing

Neptune seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Neptune to Sun [AE]
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18.2.2025 - 11.5.2026	+6.90	168.11 - 173.75 increasing	99-100 increasing	20.41-20.45 increasing	3.3 R=8.5	29.88-29.90 decreasing
9.7.2042 - 27.1.2044	+8.34	1.95-8.88 increasing	99-100 decreasing	39.57-39.61 decreasing	1.7 R=4.4	29.80-29.81 increasing

Pluto seen from Saturn:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Saturn [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Pluto to Sun [AE]
19.4.2018 - 14.9.2019	+14.38	157.60 - 175.68 increasing	99-100 increasing	23.85-24.02 decreasing	0.132 - 0.133 increasing	32.88-33.55 decreasing
20.2.2038 - 7.12.2039	+16.16	17.18-32.79 increasing	99-100 decreasing	46.65-47.35 decreasing	0.067 - 0.068 increasing	38.52-38.98 increasing
28.1.2117 - 7.10.2118	+16.35	159.04 - 160.53 increasing	99-100 increasing	40.57-40.60 increasing	0.078	49.27-49.31 decreasing
24.7.2131 - 12.2.2134	+17.11	11.44-17.32 decreasing	99-100 increasing	58.03-58.30 increasing	0.054 - 0.055 decreasing	48.48-48.69 decreasing

Mercury seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mercury to Sun [AE]
11.1.2015	weaker than +15.00	0.05	<1	19.67	0.342	0.34
5.2.-8.2. 2015	+4.85	0.40-0.59 decreasing	91-97 increasing	20.30-20.36 increasing	0.330-0.332 decreasing	0.36-0.39 increasing

Venus seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
5.2.2015	weaker than	0.08-0.09	<1	19.28	0.883	0.73

	+13.00	decreasing				
25.5.-31.5. 2015	+1.31	0.15-0.21 decreasing	99-100 increasing	20.71	0.822	0.72

Earth seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance to Earth to Sun [AE]
29.3.-10.4. 2015	+3.04	0.16-0.41 decreasing	99-100 increasing	20.98-21.00 increasing	0.837-0.838 decreasing	0.99-1.00 increasing
12.10.2015	weaker than +15.00	0.03	<1	18.98	0.927	1.00

Mars seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mars to Sun [AE]
13.2.2015	weaker than +23.00	0.03	<1	18.59	0.50	1.41
31.3.-3.4. 2016	+6.46	1.10-1.22 increasing	98-99 decreasing	21.48-21.51 decreasing	0.44	1.58-1.59 decreasing

Jupiter seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Jupiter to Sun [AE]
5.11.2017 - 24.11.2018	+1.27	1.61-6.81 increasing	94-100 decreasing	24.54-25.32 decreasing	7.8-8.1 increasing	5.36-5.45 decreasing
13.3.-14.3. 2024	weaker than +15.00	0.24	<1	14.60	13.5	5.00

Saturn seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Saturn to Sun [AE]
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22.7.-23.7.2032	weaker than +12.00	1.15	<1	10.03	16.6 R=38.6	9.02
28.10.2060 - 18.8.2063	+3.07	11.00-18.48 increasing	87-96 decreasing	24.57-26.55 decreasing	6.3-6.8 R=14.6-15.8 increasing	9.04-9.07 decreasing

Neptune seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance to Neptune to Sun [AE]
2.3.2084 - 16.8.2089	+8.86	4.43-10.15 increasing	99-100 decreasing	49.65-49.88 decreasing	1.4 R=3.5	30.04-30.11 increasing
26.9.2164 - 8.10.2166	+5.44	170.07 - 177.30 decreasing	99-100 decreasing	10.32-10.36 decreasing	6.6 R=16.8	30.10-30.13 decreasing

Pluto seen from Uranus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Uranus [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Pluto to Sun [AE]
25.5.1967 - 16.7.1969	+13.34	141.90 - 147.75 decreasing	96-98 decreasing	15.20-15.28 increasing	0.207-0.209 decreasing	31.76-32.19 decreasing
24.1.2060 - 13.8.2061	+16.90	32.50-36.25 increasing	98-99 decreasing	57.54-58.10 decreasing	0.054 - 0.055 increasing	43.64-43.96 increasing
12.9.2101 - 6.11.2104	+15.75	150.60 - 153.56 increasing	99	30.65-30.69 decreasing	0.103 - 0.104 increasing	49.02-49.17 increasing

Mercury seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mercury to
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						Sun [AE]
3.1.2015	weaker than +14.00	0.07-0.08 decreasing	<1	29.59	0.227	0.38
31.1.-1.2.2015	+5.44	0.21-0.25 decreasing	96-97 increasing	30.27-30.29 increasing	0.222	0.33-0.34 increasing

Venus seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
12.1.2015	weaker than +14.00	0.06	<1	29.24	0.571	0.73
30.4.-8.5.2015	+2.16	0.16-0.18 decreasing	99-100 increasing	30.68	0.544	0.72

Earth seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
18.2.-2.3.2015	+3.86	0.12-0.25 decreasing	99-100 increasing	30.94-30.96 increasing	0.580	0.99
1.9.2015	weaker than +19.00	0.03	<1	28.95	0.620	1.01

Mars seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mars to Sun [AE]
8.11.-20.12.2015	+7.38	0.41-0.53 increasing	99-100 decreasing	31.59-31.62 decreasing	0.296	1.66-1.67 decreasing
5.11.-6.11.2016	weaker than +21.00	0.04	<1	28.57	0.328	1.38

Jupiter seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Jupiter to Sun [AE]
12.2.-14.8.2015	+1.97	0.90-2.86 decreasing	98-100 increasing	35.05-35.33 increasing	5.6	5.33-5.39 increasing

6.6.2022	weaker than +11.00	0.02	<1	24.95	7.9	4.97
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Saturn seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Saturn to Sun [AE]
9.12.-13.12.2025	weaker than +16.00	0.45	<1	20.36	8.2 R=19.0	9.52-9.53 decreasing
5.2.2037 - 10.7.2039	+3.97	7.49-12.55 decreasing	85-96 increasing	35.69-38.22 increasing	4.4-4.7 R=10.1-10.9 decreasing	9.23-9.49 increasing

Uranus seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent brightness ["] R=ring	Distance to Uranus to Sun [AE]
1.7.2015 - 7.7.2019	+7.12	41.15-41.48 increasing	41-49 increasing	19.26-21.71 increasing	3.0-3.4 R=12.4-14.0 decreasing	19.99
25.5.2088 - 5.3.2094	+7.66	5.89-9.87 increasing	98-100 decreasing	49.11-49.75 decreasing	1.3 R=5.4	20.04-20.10 increasing
17.9.2137 - 1.8.2141	+7.12	36.58-37.37 increasing	48-57 decreasing	23.52-26.67 decreasing	2.4-2.8 R=10.1-11.5 increasing	18.30-18.40 increasing
11.12. - 28.12.2164	weaker than +16.00	1.58	<1	10.33-10.34 decreasing	6.3 R=26.1	19.79-19.80 increasing

Pluto seen from Neptune:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Neptune [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Pluto to Sun [AE]
30.8.1895 - 18.3.1898	+14.65	149.92 - 153.53 decreasing	97-98 decreasing	18.89-18.93 increasing	0.167-0.168 decreasing	47.19-47.53 decreasing
13.7.1943 - 25.5.1946	+15.66	72.60-75.08 decreasing	80-81 decreasing	32.06-32.58 increasing	0.097-0.099 decreasing	37.25-38.00 decreasing
6.8.1997 - 27.5.2002	+15.03	62.31-64.00 increasing	72-74 increasing	27.32-27.69 decreasing	0.114-0.117 increasing	29.99-30.52 increasing

27.12.2120 -8.1.2126	+17.78	12.36-15.81 decreasing	99-100 increasing	77.70-78.23 increasing	0.040-0.041 decreasing	49.01-49.23 decreasing
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Mercury seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mercury to Sun [AE]
24.1.-25.1.2015	+5.42	0.07-0.11 decreasing	98-100 increasing	33.10-33.11 increasing	0.203	0.30-0.31
15.3.-16.3.2015	weaker than +14.00	0.11	<1	32.38-32.39 increasing	0.208	0.45-0.46 decreasing
25.1.-26.1.2113	weaker than +10.00	0.10	2	49.01	0.137	0.32
21.2.-26.2.2113	+7.03	0.20-0.28 decreasing	89-96 increasing	49.63-49.70 increasing	0.135-0.136 decreasing	0.40-0.43 increasing

Venus seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
31.3.-3.4.2015	+2.40	0.08-0.10 increasing	>99	33.56	0.497	0.72
22.7.2015	weaker than +13.00	0.08	<1	32.19	0.518	0.73
5.4.-11.4.2113	+3.31	0.20 - 0.22 decreasing	98-99 increasing	50.01-50.02 increasing	0.334	0.72
31.7.-1.8.2113	weaker than +10.00	0.20	1-2	48.62	0.343	0.72

Earth seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
6.7.-7.7.2015	weaker than +16.00	0.06	<1	31.89	0.552	1.02
31.12.2015 - 11.1.2016	+4.05	0.17-0.19 decreasing	99-100 increasing	33.99-34.00 increasing	0.517-0.518 decreasing	0.98
29.4.-10.5.2113	+4.99	0.31-0.35 decreasing	97-99 increasing	50.27-50.29 increasing	0.350	1.01
8.11.-10.11.2113	weaker than +11.00	0.31-0.32 decreasing	2	48.36	0.364	0.99

Mars seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Mars to Sun [AE]
10.8.2016	weaker than +19.00	0.13	<1	31.73	0.295	1.42
11.5.-4.6.2017	+7.50	0.38-0.88 decreasing	97-100 increasing	34.80-34.92 increasing	0.268-0.270 decreasing	1.56-1.60 increasing
21.1.-22.1.2113	weaker than +14.00	0.46-0.47 increasing	2	47.91	0.196	1.46
28.2.-16.3.2114	+8.28	0.54-0.70 increasing	96-98 decreasing	50.71-50.79 decreasing	0.184-0.185 increasing	1.51-1.55 decreasing

Jupiter seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Jupiter to Sun [AE]
30.4.-24.9.1975	+1.83	2.19-2.45 increasing	98-99 decreasing	35.46-35.57 decreasing	5.5-5.6 increasing	4.95-4.96 decreasing
19.11.-14.12.1981	+7.23	3.43-3.44 decreasing	3	24.81	8.0	5.45
3.12.1987 - 2.5.1988	+1.77	2.14-2.64 decreasing	98-99 increasing	34.41-34.50 increasing	5.7	4.95-4.98 increasing

Saturn seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Saturn to Sun [AE]
13.11.1982 - 3.2.1983	+8.27	6.80-6.83 increasing	3	20.62-20.66 decreasing	8.0-8.1 R=18.7-18.8 increasing	9.72-9.75 increasing
25.7.2001 - 28.3.2003	+3.86	2.60-3.16 increasing	99-100 decreasing	39.35-39.46 increasing	4.2 R=9.8	9.03-9.09 decreasing
8.1.-12.1.2020	weaker than +18.00	0.31	<1	23.92	7.0 R=16.2	10.03

Uranus seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Uranus to Sun [AE]
8.7.1985 - 20.12.1988	+7.08	39.68-40.63 increasing	45-51 increasing	21.15-22.84 increasing	2.8-3.1 R=11.8-12.7 decreasing	19.08-19.32 increasing
12.2.-10.9.2104	+11.55	10.30-10.33 decreasing	5	30.58-30.64 increasing	2.1 R=8.8	19.78-19.82 decreasing
29.10.2143 - 21.3.2146	+8.10	8.96-11.06 decreasing	93-96 increasing	62.75-63.78 increasing	1.0 - 1.1 R=4.2-4.3 decreasing	18.49-18.62 increasing

Neptune seen from Pluto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Phase in per cent	Distance to Pluto [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Distance from Neptune to Sun [AE]
4.2.1997 - 8.1.2003	+8.16	62.30-62.88 decreasing	71-74 decreasing	27.30-27.75 decreasing	2.4-2.5 R=6.3-6.4 increasing	30.08-30.16 decreasing
25.10.2120 - 9.2.2127	+9.88	7.19-9.74 decreasing	98-99 increasing	77.67-78.30 increasing	0.9 R=2.2	30.08-30.33 increasing
3.1.2229 - 19.3.2234	+9.03	31.70-32.33 decreasing	92-93 increasing	50.61-50.81 increasing	1.3 R=3.4	29.87-29.92 increasing

Mercury seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Path velocity of Mercury [km/sec]
20.1.-23.1.2015	-4.76	0.31	21.6	58.877
5.3.-8.3.2015	-2.95	0.46-0.47 decreasing	14.2-14.5 increasing	38.833-38.938 increasing

With the path velocity's formula

$$v^2 = GM (2/r - 1/a) = GM/1AE (2/r[AE] - 1/a[AE]),$$

G is the gravitational constant, M the mass of sun, r the distance and a is the mayor semi axis. A proof can be found in Budo[1]§45 p.248.

Venus seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Path velocity of Venus [km/sec]
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			["]	
29.3.-11.5.2015	-6.00	0.72	23.2	35.290
19.6.-29.6.2015	-5.95	0.72-0.73 decreasing	22.9-23.2 increasing	34.851-34.949 increasing

Earth seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Path velocity of the Earth [km/sec]
6.1.-18.1.2015	-2.71	0.98	17.9	30.374
22.6.-27.6.2015	-2.61	1.02	17.2	29.299

Mars seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Path velocity of Mars [km/sec]
18.11.-2.12.2015	+0.99	1.66-1.67 increasing	5.6	21.996-22.011 decreasing
7.11.-16.11.2016	+0.17	1.38-1.39 decreasing	6.7-6.8 increasing	26.511-26.548 increasing

Jupiter seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Path velocity of Jupiter [km/sec]
22.7.2016 - 21.9.2017	-2.06	5.44-5.45 increasing	36.3	12.489-12.493 decreasing
11.9.2022 - 1.5.2023	-2.48	4.95-4.96 increasing	39.8-39.9 decreasing	13.724-13.731 decreasing

Saturn seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Path velocity of Saturn [km/sec]
9.11.2017 - 14.1.2018	+1.12	10.06-10.07 decreasing	16.5-16.6 increasing R=38.5	9.148-9.151 increasing

28.9.-10.10.2031	+0.64	9.03	18.4 R=42.9	10.197
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Uranus seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Path velocity of Uranus [km/sec]
14.5.2006 - 4.1.2012	+5.68	20.07-20.08 decreasing	3.2 R=13.4	6.507-6.508 increasing
14.5.2047 - 27.11.2053	+5.27	18.31	3.6 R=14.7	7.135-7.136 decreasing

Neptune seen from the sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["] R=ring	Path velocity of Neptune [km/sec]
28.8.1944 - 27.1.1983	+7.79	30.27	2.2 R=5.7	5.408
29.1.2030 - 31.5.2059	+7.72	29.86	2.3 R=5.8	5.483-5.484 decreasing

Pluto seen from the Sun:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Distance to Sun [AE]	Apparent diameter ["]	Path velocity of Pluto [km/sec]
20.11.1986 - 11.7.1992	+14.57	29.70	0.107	6.130
12.1.2110 - 28.11.2117	+16.78	49.29	0.064	3.704

Made with STELLARIUM,PLANETARIUM,VIRTUAL SKY and SOLEX.

Literature:

[1] Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutsch Verlag der Wissenschaften Berlin 1980

